

suited to rainfed wetland, RAU4009-3 and RAU4009-17, had 6.1 and 6.4% tiller infestation. Of the wetland cultivars, BRI0 was highly resistant (0.2%) (Fig.2). Maximum damage occurred on RAU4009-29 (35.8%), which also had poor tillering (6 tillers/hill). The susceptible variety Jaya had 21.8% silver shoots; the present resistant variety, IET2895, had 6.1%. ■

Honeydew excretion, feeding activity, and insect weight gain as criteria in determining levels of varietal resistance to the green leafhopper

L. Malabuyoc, research assistant; and E. A. Heinrichs, entomologist, International Rice Research Institute

Studies on the mechanism of rice resistance to the brown planthopper (BPH) have used the quantity of honeydew excretion and insect weight gain to determine levels of varietal resistance. These criteria have provided a better assessment of resistance levels than has the seedling bulk screening method. This study was conducted to determine if those parameters could be used to measure the level of resistance to the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. The susceptible variety TN1 was compared with the resistant IR29.

One-day-old adults were starved for 4 hours, weighed individually, and placed in parafilm sachets on 30-day-old plants

Each parafilm sachet contained a day-old adult green leafhopper and served as a replication.

(see photo). There were nine replications for each variety; each sachet served as a replication. After 24 hours, the insects were removed and weighed. Honeydew weight was determined by weighing the parafilm sachet with honeydew, then reweighing the sachet after wiping it dry to remove the honeydew.

The weight of the honeydew excreted on TN1 was only 2.5 times that excreted by hoppers feeding on IR29 (see table). But the weight of assimilated food, which is due primarily to weight gain,

provided more accurate information on the levels of resistance of the two varieties. The weight of assimilated food on TN1 was 13 times that on IR29.

As indicated by the amount of honeydew excreted, feeding was also substantial on the resistant IR29, but most of the intake apparently was not assimilated. Measurements of the amount of food ingested and assimilated can be used to detect levels of resistance to GLH. ■

Comparison of ingestion and metabolic utilization of food of the green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* feeding on a susceptible and a resistant variety.^a IRRI, 1979.

Variety	Honey dew wt (mg)	Qty of food ingested ^b (mg)	Wt of as-similated food ^c (mg)	Nutritive value ^d
TN1 (Susceptible)	25.587	26.380 a	0.793 a	0.030
IR29 (Resistant)	10.904	10.966 b	0.062 b	0.006

^aMean for 9 insects starved for 4 hours, then fed on 30-day-old plants for 24 hours. In a column, means followed by a different letter are significantly different at the 1% level by DMRT. ^bQty of food ingested = wt assimilated food + wt of honeydew. ^cWt of assimilated food = insect wt gain or loss due to feeding + wt loss due to metabolism. ^dNutritive value = ratio of wt of assimilated food to wt of ingested food.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Morphological studies of rice varieties that are tolerant of and susceptible to submergence as seedlings

S. Karin and B. S. Vergara, Plant Physiology Department, International Rice Research Institute

Varietal differences in submergence tolerance at the seedling stage have been reported. The morphological differences

between submergence tolerant and susceptible rice varieties at seedling stage was the objective of this study.

The seedling height measured in 10-day-old seedlings before complete submergence did not show any significant correlation with submergence tolerance. However, the tolerant varieties were generally taller than the susceptible varieties after complete submergence and recovery.

Although there was no significant correlation between the primary leaf length and survival percentage of plants when submerged in water, the tolerant varieties (all traditional) generally had longer primary leaves than the susceptible varieties (which, except for Leb Mue Nahng 111, were all improved varieties).

Table 1 shows the first and second leaf blades were longer in tolerant

Table 1. Length of the first and second leaf blades of 12 rice varieties 10 days after sowing. IRR1, November 1979.

Variety	Length (mm)	
	1st leaf blade	2d leaf blade
<i>Tolerant</i>		
FR13A	60	175
Kurkaruppan	81	147 ^a
Thavalu (15325)	69	168 ^a
Thavalu (15314)	56	183
SML Temerin	62	171 ^a
Nam Sagui 19	63	169
Av	65.2	174.5
<i>Susceptible</i>		
Leb Mue Nahng	111.47	174
T442-57	40	144
IR36	32	118
IR8	42	141
RD7	43	139
IR42	41	142
Av	40.8	143.0

^a Not fully developed leaf.

varieties when compared to the susceptible ones, except Leb Mue Nahng 111. There was a significant correlation between length of the first

leaf blade and percentage of survival ($r = 0.6715^*$). The longer leaf blades made it possible for some leaf tips to be above the water level.

Measurement of the overlapping first leaf sheath showed definitely greater overlapping for the tolerant varieties (Table 2).

The role of overlapping leaf sheaths in submergence tolerance was not clear, but one could surmise that overlapping provided a stiffer culm that prevented plant breakage or collapse at the growing point as the water receded.

There was a high correlation between overlapping of the first leaf sheath and percentage of survival ($r = 0.7261^{**}$).

The width-thickness ratio of the culm showed that the culm of tolerant varieties tended to be circular, and that of the susceptible varieties' slender or flat. There was a correlation between width-thickness ratio of seedling culm and percentage of survival ($r = -0.6450^*$).

The shape of the culm probably was

Table 2. Overlapping of the first leaf sheath at 3 cm above the seed of 10-day-old seedlings. IRR1, December 1979.

Variety	Overlapping (microns)
<i>Tolerant</i>	
FR13A	601
Kurkaruppan	639
Thavalu (15325)	608
Thavalu (15314)	505
SML Temerin	594
Nam Sagui 19	460
Av	568
<i>Susceptible</i>	
Leb Mue Nahng 111	430
T442-57	410
IR36	213
RD7	364
IR42	289
Av	353

responsible also for the degree of overlapping of the leaf sheath or vice versa. There was a high correlation ($r = -0.7384^*$) between the length of overlapping and the width-thickness ratio of the culm. The round culms had more overlapping leaf sheaths than the flat culms. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Variation in chlorophyll of rice seedlings under low temperature

S. K. Bardhan Roy and S. Biswas, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India

The normal, green color of rice seedling leaves is a desirable characteristic in areas where low temperature prevails early in the growing season. Low temperature during the early growth stages causes yellowing of leaves and stunting. This study evaluates the effect of low temperature on chlorophyll production. It also correlates chlorophyll production with subsequent expression of leaf discoloration.

Seeds of three cultivars — G. S. 10231 (japonica), CNM20 (a mutant of IR8), and IR8 — were sown at different times so the cultivars were exposed to variable diurnal temperatures of 9.3°C/25.2°C—14.90°C/28.8°C. Samples

for chlorophyll estimation were taken at 30, 60, and 90 days after sowing (DS), and visual ratings for discoloration were recorded.

Chlorophyll estimation was done by following the method described by Yoshida, Forno, Cock, and Gomez (1976). The chlorophyll absorbance on the leaf tissue extract at 645 and 665 mμ were measured by Spectronic-20. The total chlorophyll content was calculated as the sum of chlorophyll "a" and "b" (mg/g fresh wt).

A high value of total chlorophyll content was noted (Table 1) during high temperatures. Total chlorophyll content was gradually reduced with decreasing temperature (22.3°C—9.1°C). But with the age of plants (90 DS), total chlorophyll increased despite lower temperature.

Expression of leaf color did not show a close relationship with total

Individuals, organizations, and media who wish additional details of information presented in IRRN should write directly to the authors.

chlorophyll in all the cultivars. It has been reported that visual differences in greenness in sorghum do not necessarily mean real differences in chlorophyll content. Lines that are alike may or may not contain the same kind and amounts of chlorophyll. A higher chlorophyll a-b ratio was observed at lower temperature (Table 2), suggesting that the production of chlorophyll 'b' suffered more in a cool environment. ■